

Original Article

Exploring Early Marriage in Rural Sindh: Socio-Cultural Factors and Effects on Women' Health and Education

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Abstract

Child marriage remains an overlooked social issue at the grassroots level in Pakistani society with minimal public discussion and discourse. The people in traditional societies are unaware about the harmful impacts of child marriages on socio-cultural, educational and psychological wellbeing of women in the society. The real challenges due to this phenomenon are generally neglected in the academic research. Therefore, this study has been designed to assess the impact of early marriages on life of rural women living in the coastal region of Sindh province in Pakistan. This qualitative research study conducted through interviews. Selected women were early married women from rural areas in district Thatta. Study involved eight women participants aged between 17 to 34. Most of them were married between the ages of 10 to 17 by their parents in close family relatives. These women belonged to a low socio-economic background. This study identified societal norms and customs, poverty and economic insecurity, and the community pressure as the socio-cultural factors of early marriages. Furthermore, it highlights the unfavourable psychological effects of early marriages on health of women and educational barriers faced by these women due to early marriage. This study also noticed lack of awareness about legal age of women and due rights of women in the study area. Therefore, it recommends the need of awareness campaigns for the women rights and taking concrete measure for socio-economic uplift of women.

Keywords: Early Marriages, Socio-Economic Conditions, Coastal Communities, Women Health, Female Education, Rural Sindh

Introduction

When a child under "18 years old" gets married, this is something that has been happening for a very long time all over the world. It is also known as "early marriage" or "child marriage". (Mim, 2017). Paul and Mondal (2021) said that Child marriage is when someone under the age of 18 gets married. This is against the Convention on the Rights of the Child. The practice of child marriage has negative impacts on the health, dignity, and independence of girls. Yet early marriage is very common in Asian countries, as per UNICEF's 2020 report, and has negative effects on both genders, with girls facing more concerns related to early marriage than boys (Hossain, Abdulla et al. 2022). In the world, about 12 million girls get married before they turn 18 every year. In sub-Saharan Africa, where 38% of girls are affected, South Asia and Latin America also have high rates of child marriage, with 30% and 25% of girls affected, respectively. In Bangladesh, 59% of women are married before the age of 18, and in the Dominican Republic and Brazil, 36% of women are married before they reach that age. Similarly, in Afghanistan, at least one out of every three young girls is married before the age of 18. In Indonesia, approximately 11% of marriages involve children under the age of 18 and in Pakistan, nearly 40% of women are married before they turn 18 years old. The UNICEF Report 2022 states that 19 million girls in Pakistan became child brides (Khan, 2022). In Pakistani society, many people believe that child marriages are a way to protect young girls. However, getting

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married at a young age can make girls vulnerable to negative effects on their health, education and social well-being. This includes facing gender inequality, health issues, poverty, and violence. It's important to understand that early marriages can harm girls and hinder their overall development and empowerment (Bhanji and Punjani 2014). It has also been observed that the girls who are taken out of school and married off at a young age become completely dependent on their husbands (Rehman et al. 2014). In patriarchal societies, people prefer young and uneducated brides because they believe they will be more obedient. This means that girls miss out on education and reinforce gender inequality (Mim, 2017). Early marriages are prevalent in rural and urban areas, posing significant challenges to the overall health and education of girls. Girls often drop out of school and become mothers at a young age, resulting in various health complications. Previous research has primarily focused on maternal health and malnutrition, neglecting psychological factors associated with early marriage (Nour, 2006). The Sindh province of Pakistan is also facing this issue of early marriages especially in the rural and remote area. Coastal people living in the Thata district belong to low socio-economic background and combating variety of social issues and problems (Jagirani et al., 2021). There is a rare knowledge and studies available about this topic in the coastal region of Sindh. This study aims to investigate socio-cultural factors responsible for early marriages in Pakistan and understand the effects of early marriages on the health and education of women in the study area.

Literature Review

Early marriage has been a long-standing tradition in many societies, affecting the education and health of young girls, especially in developing countries. This literature review examines how early marriages impact girls' education and health. Article 16 of the 1979 Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women states a minimum age requirement for marriage for the women and child marriages are not allowed. This means that it is against the law for children to get married at early ages (UN, 1980).

Early marriage, also known as child marriage, is assumed when two people get married or enter a union when one or both falls under 18 years of age (Nwose et al. 2018; WHO, 2013). In South Asian region, including Pakistan, child marriage is a dominant practice that is often justified based on social, cultural, and religious traditions. Unfortunately, many young girls who are forced into such marriages face physical, educational, psychological, and economic disadvantages that continue throughout their lives (Roswiyani et al., 2022). Pakistan is a country that has an average of 19 million child brides, and one-sixth of young women were wed during their childhood. Pakistan ranks as the 6th highest country in the World for child marriages (UNICEF, 2018). Practice of child marriage is often justified to safeguard the virtue of young girls since any instance of premarital sexual activity and pregnancy is viewed as a source of dishonor for the family. Child marriage puts young girls at risk of experiencing sexual, physical, and emotional violence because of the unequal power dynamic present in the marital relationship (Fuseini et al. 2019). Early marriages are shaped by a variety of factors, highlighting the influence of male dominance, parental unawareness, limited awareness of alternative options, societal pressure, the perception of girls as burdens, parents' desire to protect their daughters, and the aspiration to enhance the family's social standing (Ahmed et al., 2013). It is recommended that children should not be allowed for marriage before the age of 18 because they do not have enough maturity to fulfill their responsibilities. When a girl is married, she is expected to take on multiple responsibilities and roles such as being a wife, a daughter-in-law housekeeper, a caretaker, and a mother (Ambert, 2012).

Child marriage happens because families may be very poor, and it has many negative effects on a girl's health. These effects include a higher chance of getting diseases that are passed through sex, getting cervical cancer, getting malaria, dying while giving birth, and having a problem called obstetric fistula (Nour, 2006). Girls who get married at a young age are more likely to get sexually transmitted diseases like HIV and HPV compared to unmarried girls. In sub-Saharan Africa, girls aged 15-19 have a higher risk of getting HIV compared to boys of the same age (Schwärtlander et al., 2001). Child marriage not only affects young girls but also their children. Girls who get pregnant at a young age face many difficulties. When teenage girls have babies, their babies are more likely to be born too early and too small and their children may experience poor physical health and malnutrition (Roswiyani et al., 2022). Chances of child mortality are also higher in early age marriages as compared to babies born to older mothers. Babies born to mothers under the age of 20 have a 73% higher chance of dying than babies born to older mothers. be born too soon and die when they are newborns, infants, or young children (Nour, 2006). The positive aspect of early marriage is that women who get married at a young age tend to have a higher fertility rate than those who marry later in life. As a result, men tend to marry young girls. For example, women in Bangladesh who marry at a later age tend to have fewer children compared to those who marry at an early age (Muazzam et al.,

2014). Marrying at a young age can disrupt the future of young girls in terms of their education, social life, and finances. Teenage girls who are married may not have the opportunity to attend school or spend time with friends, which can limit their personal growth and development. This can impact their future opportunities for employment and financial independence (Muazzam et al., 2014).

Early marriage has an impact on the physical and psychological health of newlyweds, and it also results in the loss of education, especially for young brides. According to the UNFPA's report the decline in secondary-level students, which was approximately 3.4% in 2017, is a violation of human rights due to early marriage. (Shabbar and Manzoor, 2022). The issue of child marriages is because of few factors such as lack of education, and gender discrimination. Early marriage for girls increases the likelihood of experiencing physical, emotional, and sexual violence, as well as dropping out of school (Fatima, 2023). Many girls leave school because they get married early. This means that the victim girls of early marriages could not learn important skills and knowledge that could help them in becoming a good and well-informed mother in the future (Ocharo et al., 2015). When a woman is educated, she is more likely to be a capable and informed mother, a productive and higher-paid worker, a knowledgeable citizen, a confident person, and a skilled decision-maker (Kabeer, 1991). It is also observed that in various communities, priority is given to the education of boys over girls, which results in daughters remaining uneducated while sons are educated. And daughters are married off without completing their education (Nguyen et al., 2016). In current era, there is a tradition of dowry in our society, while girls from poor families are married off early because they are less educated, which means their parents do not have to give a higher dowry. After all, it is believed that a less educated girl cannot make decisions for herself and thus, she would be a good homemaker (Edmeades et al., 2015). Like other regions the Pakistani society also facing variety of social problems. Especially the women are vulnerable group in the society and they have various health and education challenges in the Sindh province (Guriro et al., 2019; Masood et al., 2020). Therefore, it is very much pertinent to investigate the rural society of Sindh province in Pakistan and its social problems especially focusing the issues and rights of women population.

Material and Method

In this study, we have used a qualitative research methodology to identify the socio-cultural factors of early marriage and investigate how early marriage affects the health and education of adolescent girls. We collected primary data from 08 married women who had been married at an early age by their parents. All women participants were from the coastal areas of Thatta district. The data was collected through in-depth interviews, which allowed us to explore the participants' personal experiences and perspectives regarding the factors behind early marriage and know the impact of early marriage on their education and health.

Demographic Characteristics

The study included women participants of aged 17 to 34 years. All of victim women got married during the period of 10 to 17 years of age in their lives. Majority of the respondents belonged to rural settings in the Thatta district particularly in the coastal area villages. This area in the Sindh province is characterized through low income levels of the people and resources due to climate change factors. The occupational categories of both the respondents and their husbands indicated that most participants were part of the low socio-economic class. Among them, three respondents belonged to the low socio-economic class and assumed the role of housewives in their homes. During the interviews it was found that most respondents had not received a formal education in their lives. Only one participant had got formal education. Majority of the women were also engaged in agriculture farming and livestock rearing along with their male partners.

Socio-Cultural Factors of Early Marriage

According to most responses, early marriages are frequently influenced by a combination of socio-cultural factors in the study area. One significant factor observed was the societal norms prevailing in the remote traditional societies like the rural societies of coastal region in the Sindh province. Societal expectation of preserving parental honor, where marrying daughters at a young age is seen to maintain a family reputation and safeguard against perceived risks. Financial constraints resulting from poverty and economic insecurity also contribute to early marriages, as families may view them to reduce financial burdens and ensure the well-being of their daughters. The peer and community pressure also encourage and enforce families to take decisions of early marriages. The fear of judgment or criticism from society acts as a motivating factor, pushing families to opt for early marriages to align with old customs and avoid negative societal opinions.

These observations can be judged from below response of the participant:

“One respondent shared that their parents arranged their marriage quickly due to societal pressure and negative comments received after a previous relationship ended”. [Participant in late twenties, educated, married at the age of 16 years]

Participants informed that Child marriages are widespread in rural areas and societal norms dictate and encourage the early marriage of children. The reply of one participant endorse it as follows:

“My brother's marriage was arranged when I was only 10 years old, and as a result, they proposed my marriage as a substitute. As a result of these relationships,

I got married at that age”. [Participant in early forties, uneducated, married at the age of 10 years]

Majority of the participants identified economic insecurity and poverty as the main factor. One participant mentioned it as follows:

“Due to unfavorable financial family circumstances and poverty, my sister and I were married at a young age. I was 16 years old, and my sister was 15.

Our parents, worried about our future, decided to arrange our marriages early”. [Participant in early twenties, uneducated, married at the age of 17 years].

Out of 08 respondents, 06 agreed that societal norms are a major factor contributing to our early marriages. Majority women also indicated the economic insecurity and poverty as another socio-cultural factors in addition to community pressure for early marriage. When we inquired about the any information about the legal age of marriage it was observed that no women know about it.

The research conducted in this study shares several similarities with the findings of Ahmed et al. (2013). Both studies highlight the influence of societal pressure as a contributing factor to the prevalence of early marriages. Additionally, both studies identify parents' desire to protect their daughters and the aspiration to enhance the family's social standing as significant factors associated with early marriages.

Effects of Early Marriage on Women s' Health

According to our study, getting married at a young age can have several effect on a person's mental well-being. It can make them less interested in talking to others and less motivated to socialize. Furthermore, they may find it difficult to build strong relationships or feel positive emotions toward others. This can be noted in the response of one victim of early marriage as follows:

“The impact on my mental health was so profound that it made me cry, which resulted in my deteriorating health during my pregnancy and the premature birth of my baby. Still I feel fear of pregnancy in my life [Participant in early forties, married at the age of 15 years].

We observed that the Early marriage gives rise to various challenges. It changed the relationship of women with their relatives. According to majority of the respondents, it significantly impacted the mental well-being of women as mentioned by one participant:

“I was mentally distressed, and it took me a year to adjust to my in-laws' place. I couldn't make any decisions on my own, which prolonged the process of adaptation. During my pregnancy, I also felt very disturbed, and at night, I would stay awake, praying and performing my prayers.” [Participant in early twenties, married at the age of 16 years]

Another women participant replied as follows:

“Due to getting married early, I lost time and freedom. I also became physically very weak which greatly affected my mental health. I felt very lonely and often perceived myself as being alone.” [Participant in early thirties, married at the age of 16 years]

According to our study, early marriage can lead to various difficulties for girls during pregnancy. One of the reasons is the increased risk of physical health issues and malnutrition at a young age, as indicated by (Nabila, Roswiyani et al., 2022). However, there is a contradiction between their findings and this research. Our research

suggests that mental stress or psychological problems can also contribute to the challenges faced by girls in early pregnancy.

Effects of Early Marriage on Education of Women

In study area we observed that majority of the participant women had trouble in going to school. Out of the 8 women, we asked, a surprising 5 of them couldn't continue their education because they got married at a young age. This meant they couldn't go to school like they wanted to. It was a big disappointment for them, as they had dreams of learning more and getting a formal and basic education. The early marriage made it difficult for them to pursue their education, and it had a lasting impact on their lives. One of the participant said:

“I was studying at secondary level when I got married. But due to early marriage, my education remained incomplete and I left school. Even after marriage, I expressed my desire to continue my studies, but my in-laws did not support me”. [Participant in early twenties, educated, married at the age of 15 years]

One of the participant replied that:

“I feel a deep regret that my basic education remained incomplete due to marriage, and it continues to sadden me even today. After getting married, it became significantly challenging to continue my studies as the responsibilities of raising children take precedence. It became difficult to give attention to academic pursuits.” [Participant in late twenties, uneducated, married at the age of 15 years]

According to our findings, a lack of education has a significant impact on girls' lives, affecting their skill development, self-esteem, and overall well-being. Education plays a crucial role in shaping their prospects. If we compare the studies conducted by Shabbar and Manzoor (2022) and Fatima (2023), it is evident that a lack of education contributes to a decline in secondary-level students and increases the likelihood of girls experiencing physical, emotional, and sexual violence, as well as dropping out of school. These factors significantly impact the lives of girls who face these challenges.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, this research sheds light on the prevalence of early marriages among young individuals in rural settings, particularly those from low socio-economic backgrounds. Societal norms, poverty and economic insecurity, and the pressure from community were identified as key socio-cultural factors behind the early marriages in rural areas of Sindh, Pakistan. The study highlighted the psychological effects of early marriage, including decreased socialization, challenges in building relationships, and negative impacts on mental well-being. Furthermore, the research emphasized the adverse impact of early marriage on education, with many participants unable to continue their schooling and experiencing long-term regret. These findings underscore the urgent need for addressing societal norms, providing support for families in vulnerable circumstances, and prioritizing access to education for young girls. By addressing these issues, we can work towards empowering individuals, improving mental health outcomes, and fostering a brighter future for those affected by early marriages.

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